

Improving Process Monitoring via Dynamic Multi-Fidelity Modeling

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Abstract: We study real-time process monitoring, where employed online sensors yield inaccurate information. A multi-fidelity (MF) modeling approach is adopted that integrates dynamic information from online, low-fidelity (LF) data with infrequent, high-fidelity (HF) laboratory measurements. The proposed methodology is demonstrated on a composition monitoring problem derived from real oil refinery operations. The developed MF model exhibits a significant improvement in accuracy with respect to both LF data (online sensor) and the HF model (standard soft sensor). The results highlight the potential of MF modeling for improving process monitoring and control through the integration of diverse data sources.

Keywords: Dynamic models, Multi-fidelity models, Gaussian processes, Feature selection

1. INTRODUCTION

Effective monitoring and control are critical for optimizing industrial operations (Sumasto et al., 2023), where a prerequisite is a precise and timely gathering of process information by sensing of the underlying quantities. Direct sensing can be performed by hard sensors via online or lab analyzers, where lab sensorics is used when an online alternative is unavailable, costly, or unreliable. Soft sensors (Kadlec et al., 2009) can be used to obtain the desired information in real time. They employ prediction models combining other online-sensor data. Online hard/soft sensors seemingly circumvent the need for lab analyses, yet on-demand calibration by the lab measurements is still necessary to maintain their accuracy.

Consequently, industrial plants involve several online sensors, which provide large amounts of data, and are even accompanied with infrequent lab measurement records. These datasets only rarely find an advanced use, beyond the single-point calibration. The so-called multi-fidelity (MF) modeling () promises to exploit various related or duplicate datasets and fuse the information contained. Our goal here is to find a joint use of laboratory high-

fidelity (HF) data and the low-fidelity (LF) data from online sensors to improve the industrial monitoring.

Data-based modeling is at the core of our endeavor. Data-based models leverage historical data and have been applied successfully across several industrial sectors (). There are several milestones of designing a data-based model: data processing, selection of model structure (linear/non-linear, static/dynamic, parametric/non-parametric), feature selection, model training. Above all, a crucial importance must be paid to the feature selection, which is a key prerequisite for choosing an appropriate structure of a prediction model. Techniques such as principal component analysis, partial least squares, and many more (Bastos et al., 2022) have been used successfully. Non-parametric approaches can be used in model development, such as Gaussian Process Regression (GPR) (Rasmussen, 2004) that has also shown good performance when applied to industrial tasks (Ge et al., 2011). Gaussian processes also found use in MF modeling (Kadlec et al., 2009). When dealing with high-dimensional datasets, feature selection is paramount (Perdikaris et al., 2015).

This study investigates MF models for industrial monitoring by integrating online sensor data with laboratory measurements to boost predictive accuracy. Combining frequent LF data with precise HF data, our approach supports reliable, timely monitoring. Using GPR within the MF framework, this method provides output predictions and quantifies uncertainties, reinforcing decision

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Fig. 1. Model development flowchart.

robustness. Additionally, we study the use of dynamic models within the MF modeling framework.

2. PROBLEM DEFINITION

We assume two distinct datasets: historical LF data from online sensors and HF data from laboratory measurements. The LF data are collected continuously at a high sampling frequency. In contrast, HF data are obtained less frequently through, serving as reference points for calibrating and validating the online sensors. Let us define the time instant sets as follows: $\mathcal{T}_{\text{LF}} = \{t_1, t_2, \dots, t_{n_{\text{LF}}}\}$ representing the time instants when LF measurements are taken and $\mathcal{T}_{\text{HF}} = \{\tau_1, \tau_2, \dots, \tau_{n_{\text{HF}}}\}$ representing the time instants of laboratory samples. Typically, $n_{\text{HF}} \ll n_{\text{LF}}$. The associated index sets are denoted as \mathcal{I}_{LF} and \mathcal{I}_{HF} , respectively. We seek a predictive model that can accurately relate the process variables and $\mathbf{x} \in \mathbb{R}^{n_x}$ and the desired quantity $y \in \mathbb{R}$.

A linear model predicting the i^{th} instant reads as:

$$\hat{y}_i = \boldsymbol{\theta}^\top \boldsymbol{\varphi}_i + \epsilon_i, \quad (1)$$

where \hat{y}_i is the predicted output, $\boldsymbol{\varphi}_i$ is a vector of regressors, and $\boldsymbol{\theta}$ is a vector of model parameters. The error term ϵ_i captures discrepancies due to measurement errors or unmodelled variability. A nonlinear model can be defined equivalently as:

$$\hat{y}_i = f(\boldsymbol{\theta}_i, \boldsymbol{\varphi}_i). \quad (2)$$

The specific form of $\boldsymbol{\varphi}_i$ depends on whether a *static* or *dynamic* modeling approach is selected: A) *Static model* with $\boldsymbol{\varphi}_i = \mathbf{x}_i$.

B) *Dynamic model* with $\boldsymbol{\varphi}_i$ that includes lagged values, given by $\boldsymbol{\varphi}_i = [\mathbf{x}_{i-1}, \dots, \mathbf{x}_{i-j}, y_{i-1}, \dots, y_{i-k}]^\top$.

3. METHODOLOGY

We outline the key steps of model development (see Fig. 1).

3.1 Pre-processing

Raw data denoted as \mathbf{X}_{raw} , often exhibit significant correlations and contain non-random noise (plant start-ups or shutdowns, various disturbance scenarios), outliers, and missing values. These must be addressed before model training by reducing noise, handling missing data and outliers (FÅqber et al., 2024).

Outlier detection can be performed using the Minimum Covariance Determinant (MCD) method (Rousseeuw and Driessen, 1999), a robust statistical technique that leverages Mahalanobis distance to identify anomalous data points by minimizing the determinant of the sample covariance matrix \mathbf{S} . The distance measure is given by:

$$d_i = \sqrt{(\mathbf{v}_i - \boldsymbol{\mu})^\top \mathbf{S}^{-1} (\mathbf{v}_i - \boldsymbol{\mu})}, \quad (3)$$

where \mathbf{v}_i stands for data vector as $\mathbf{V} = (\mathbf{X} \ \mathbf{y})^\top$ and $\boldsymbol{\mu}$ is the mean vector of the same dimension. 3σ rule can be applied to classify outliers.

In the context of dynamic model training, standard interpolation methods can be applied to replace outliers while preserving the temporal relationships between variables.

3.2 Feature Selection

The objective of feature selection is to identify the subset of process variables Φ that contribute most significantly to the accurate and reliable prediction. By including only the most relevant variables, we improve model interpretability and computational efficiency and reduce the likelihood of overfitting (Li et al., 2017). The most common methods for feature selection are briefly reviewed.

Principal Component Analysis (PCA) reduces dimensionality by transforming the original dataset into a new set of uncorrelated variables, maximizing variance and minimizing information loss (Pearson, 1901).

Partial Least Squares (PLS) Regression identifies latent variables that explain the most variance in both the dependent variable \mathbf{y} , and independent variables \mathbf{X}_{proc} , effectively handling multicollinearity. The PLS approach can be formulated as:

$$\mathbf{X}_{\text{proc}} = \mathbf{T} \mathbf{P}^\top + \mathbf{E}, \quad (4)$$

$$\mathbf{y} = \mathbf{U} \mathbf{q} + \mathbf{r}. \quad (5)$$

Here, \mathbf{T} and \mathbf{U} denote the score matrices, \mathbf{P} and \mathbf{q} represent the weight matrix and vector, respectively, and \mathbf{E} and \mathbf{r} are the error terms (Geladi and Kowalski, 1986).

LASSO regression incorporates an ℓ_1 penalty to promote model sparsity. It solves the following problem:

$$\min_{\boldsymbol{\theta}} \frac{1}{2} \sum_{i=1}^N (y_i - \boldsymbol{\theta}^\top \boldsymbol{\varphi}_i)^2 + \lambda \|\boldsymbol{\theta}\|_1, \quad (6)$$

where λ is a tuning parameter that controls the strength of the penalty (Santosa and Symes, 1986).

Stepwise Regression (SR) systematically adds or removes variables in a multilinear model based on their statistical significance. At each step, the p -value of an F -statistic determine whether to add or remove a regressor. Alternatively, criteria such as the Akaike Information Criterion (AIC, minimizes information loss), the Corrected Akaike Information Criterion (AICc, adjusts AIC for small sample sizes), and the Bayesian Information Criterion (BIC, penalizes model complexity more strictly, favoring simpler models for larger datasets) can also guide the feature selection process (Efroymson, 1960).

In addition to the aforementioned methods, the model structure can be enhanced by expert process knowledge. We selected six relevant variables, reducing the dataset from $N \hat{=} 1085$ to $N \hat{=} 6$.

3.3 Model Training

Model (1) can be fitted to the available data via:

$$\min_{\theta} \frac{1}{2} \|\mathbf{y}_l - \hat{\mathbf{y}}_l\|_2^2 \equiv \min_{\theta} \frac{1}{2} \sum_{i=1}^{n_l} (y_{l,i} - \hat{y}_{l,i})^2 \quad (7a)$$

$$\text{s.t. } y_{l,i} = \theta^\top \boldsymbol{\varphi}_{l,i} \text{ or } y_{l,i} = f(\theta^\top, \boldsymbol{\varphi}_{l,i}), \forall i \in \mathcal{I}_l \quad (7b)$$

where $l \in \{\text{HF}, \text{LF}\}$ distinguishes the HF or LF model.

3.4 Multi-fidelity Model Training

The MF combines trained HF and LF models. The regressor matrix Φ_{MF} integrates all data:

$$\boldsymbol{\varphi}_{\text{MF},i} = \left(\boldsymbol{\varphi}_{\text{HF},i}^\top, \boldsymbol{\varphi}_{\text{LF},i}^\top, \hat{\mathbf{y}}_{\text{LF}}^\top, \mathbf{y}_{\text{LF}}^\top \right)^\top, \forall i \in \mathcal{I}_{\text{HF}}. \quad (8)$$

After an obligatory feature selection step, the MF model can be trained by GPR. The GP can be defined as:

$$\hat{\mathbf{y}}_{\text{MF}} \sim \mathcal{GP}(m(\boldsymbol{\kappa}), k(\boldsymbol{\kappa}, \boldsymbol{\kappa}')), \quad (9)$$

where $\boldsymbol{\kappa}$ represents the predictors derived from the feature-selected dataset Φ_{MF} , $m(\boldsymbol{\kappa})$ is the mean function representing the expected value of the output, and $k(\boldsymbol{\kappa}, \boldsymbol{\kappa}')$ is the covariance function (kernel) that defines the correlation between the output data. A composite kernel used in this model is defined as:

$$k(\boldsymbol{\kappa}, \boldsymbol{\kappa}') = C \cdot e^{-M} + e^{-\frac{2 \sin^2 M}{\ell^2}} + \sigma^2 \delta_{\boldsymbol{\kappa}, \boldsymbol{\kappa}'}, \quad (10)$$

where $M = \frac{\|\boldsymbol{\kappa} - \boldsymbol{\kappa}'\|^2}{2}$. The 1st term represents a constant kernel C , followed by the RBF kernel, capturing smooth variations. The 3rd term models periodicity with a sinusoidal kernel, while the last (white kernel) term accounts for noise using the Kronecker delta function $\delta_{\boldsymbol{\kappa}, \boldsymbol{\kappa}'}$. The parameter ℓ is the length scale, determining the influence between points, and σ^2 is the noise variance.

4. AN INDUSTRIAL CASE STUDY

The alkylation process is essential in refineries for producing high-octane branched isoparaffins, i.e., alkylate, a key component of clean gasoline. The production involves the reaction of C_3 – C_4 olefins with isobutane (i- C_4) using an acid catalyst. The reaction pathway initiates with the protonation of the olefin, leading to the formation of carbonium cations that react further to produce C_8 isomers (Speight, 2020; PALL Corporation and Chemicals, 2018).

Maintaining an optimal ratio of reactants is critical for efficient alkylate production. Online analyzers strategically placed in the plant (see Fig. 2) measure the concentration of key components in the feed and recycle streams, providing real-time data for effective process control. The ability to accurately predict and correct deviations in analyzer data modeling is essential to enhance overall process efficiency and reduce undesirable by-products.

We utilize a comprehensive dataset \mathbf{X}_{raw} spanning over six months of alkylate production, comprising over a thousand process variables from online sensors, online analyzers, and laboratory samples, totaling over $N \times 1085$ data points. Among these variables, we focus on a specific analyzer monitoring the i- C_4 concentration in the recycle stream (A_3 in Fig. 2), which has shown

unreliable performance. This inconsistency results in the recycling of excess i- C_4 , imposing an unnecessary load on downstream operations as the recycled material must undergo additional post-reaction heating and treatment.

5. IMPLEMENTATION

To ensure confidentiality, we standardize the raw data \mathbf{X}_{raw} and apply the data cleaning methods outlined in Section 3. Subsequently, we split the pre-processed data \mathbf{X}_{proc} into training and testing sets, using a 60-40% ratio. This approach is necessary due to the limited availability of HF data, ensuring that both sets exhibit similar trends while maintaining chronological date time sequences. The chosen time frame spans four months for training and two months for testing, which is particularly relevant as seasonal variations during this period can significantly influence process dynamics, including the characteristics of processed olefins and isobutane.

To select relevant, non-redundant features, we apply the statistical feature selection methods of Section 3.2 on the preprocessed dataset \mathbf{X}_{proc} , which can be derived from either LF or HF sources. We consider one reduced dataset Φ_{MF} — a subset of six input variables — that feeds into each model training step (compare Fig. 1). These selected variables, highlighted in Fig. 2, include four concentrations measured by online analyzers located in the mixing section (olefin feed propylene — AT1, deisobutanizer recycle propane — AT2, isobutane — AT3, and *n*-butane — AT4), and two flow rates (recycled fresh acid — FC5, and alkylate to storage — FC6). In this stage, we train a simple and efficient HF model, aiming to predict the HF data $\hat{\mathbf{y}}_{\text{HF}}$. The model structure is given by Eq. 2, and its predictions are illustrated with a purple dashed line in Fig. 3.

To train the dynamic LF model, we first apply PLS on the processed feature set \mathbf{X}_{proc} , reducing the six selected variables into principal components (PCs). We calculate the explained variance (EV) as a function of the number of PCs and select the “elbow” point on the variance plot, where adding additional PCs offers minimal gain in information. This approach led to the selection of four PCs, which account for approximately 95% of the EV.

Following the dimensionality reduction, we perform dynamic system identification on the LF data using the open-source SIPPY - Systems Identification Package for Python (Armenise et al., 2018). We use the PARSIM-K robust identification method (Pannocchia and Calosi, 2010), which is particularly suitable for closed-loop data, to ensure that the dynamic model $\hat{\mathbf{y}}_{\text{LF}}$ accurately represents the system dynamics with the fewest parameters necessary. To balance model accuracy with simplicity, we compute three selection criteria (AIC, AICc, and BIC from Section 3.2) to determine the optimal model order. The AIC suggested a 4th order model, AICc recommended a 10th order, and BIC proposed a 3rd order. We selected the 4th order model based on AIC, achieving

Fig. 2. A simplified schematic representation of an alkylation unit divided into upstream — mixing and reaction section and the downstream separation section. The analyzer, highlighted in red as A3, approximates the dependent variable \mathbf{y}_{LF} . The other highlighted variables represent the six variables selected through feature selection.

an effective trade-off between goodness of fit and model complexity.

In developing the MF model, we utilize the Python `scikit-learn` library (Pedregosa et al., 2011). We experimentally tuned a composite kernel to the form (??) to capture distinct aspects of the data. We perform feature selection by PCA on LF data containing features of LF model and LF model as a feature by itself. This allows us to reduce the seven variables to four PCs using the “elbow” method. The MF model is trained using the GP to predict the deviations $\Delta_{HF,i} = \mathbf{y}_{HF,i} - \mathbf{y}_{LF,i}$, $\forall i \in \mathcal{I}_{HF}$.

6. RESULTS

Table 1 presents the RMSE comparison for various feature selection methods applied to the pre-processed low-fidelity dataset (LF- \mathbf{X}_{proc}), where the resulting features were used in each model training. The results indicate that PCA offers the most accurate performance, achieving RMSE values of 0.16 for training and 0.21 for testing. While PCA provides superior accuracy, it relies on 75 uncorrelated PCs, which makes it less practical for industrial applications due to sensor maintenance challenges. PLS achieves slightly worse RMSE values of 0.28 for training and 0.32 for testing. LASSO yields RMSE values of 0.30 for both the training and testing sets, promoting sparsity in the model, although it does not perform as well as PCA or PLS in this instance. SR emerges as the most suitable option for balancing predictive accuracy and simplicity, achieving RMSE values of 0.21 for training and 0.24 for testing.

Additionally, we consulted with our industrial partner to ensure that the selection aligns with practical insights regarding process input-output behavior. Based on the insights gained, necessary adjustments were made to

Table 1. RMSE comparison for the used feature selection methods on the LF dataset.

Method	Training RMSE	Testing RMSE
PCA	0.16	0.21
PLS	0.28	0.32
LASSO	0.30	0.30
SR	0.21	0.24

substitute any unsuitable variables, enhancing the overall robustness of the selected subset.

Table 2 evaluates predictive performance of all trained models using the RMSE metric against the HF data \mathbf{y}_{HF} on a standardized dataset. Firstly, the RMSE values for the current online analyzer’s data \mathbf{y}_{LF} compared to lab-measured data \mathbf{y}_{HF} are 0.63 for training and 0.80 for testing, indicating poor performance. Focusing on the HF model $\hat{\mathbf{y}}_{HF}$, we observe a notable discrepancy between its training and testing outcomes. Specifically, while the model achieves an RMSE of 0.18 on the training dataset, this value increases to 1.01 on the testing dataset, indicating reduced generalization to unseen data. Visual inspection suggests that the HF model captures the trends in the HF data effectively, as shown by the close alignment in Fig. 3. The observed increase in RMSE on the testing data suggests that the variables selected through feature selection methods, in collaboration with process engineers, may not align well with those preferred by a high-fidelity (HF)-specific approach. Moreover, the limited availability of HF data restricts the model’s capacity to fully capture the variability present in the HF dataset.

The resulting dynamic LF model $\hat{\mathbf{y}}_{LF}$, produces RMSE values of 0.52 for training and 0.91 for testing, showcasing moderate improvements over the LF data but still limited generalization. Although the dynamic model exhibited a slightly higher RMSE (0.91) when compared

Fig. 3. Predictions of the normalized concentration on the training (top), and testing (bottom) sets as data series.

to the current online analyzer (0.80), a closer examination shows that it more accurately followed the trend of the laboratory samples, which were not included in its training data. This indicates that, despite the RMSE difference, the dynamic model is better equipped to capture time-dependent patterns and provides more reliable predictions of the actual process behavior, underscoring its robustness beyond what RMSE alone suggests.

The multi-fidelity model $\hat{\mathbf{y}}_{\text{MF}}$, which utilizes a GP, shows a significant improvement in accuracy, with RMSE values of 0.31 for training and 0.38 for testing. Fig. 3 demonstrates that the MF model significantly enhances predictive accuracy compared to both LF and HF models. In the figures, the blue solid line represents the original LF data (\mathbf{y}_{LF}), while the black dashed line shows the MF model adjusted HF predictions ($\hat{\mathbf{y}}_{\text{MF}}$). Red markers indicate HF laboratory data, and the black shaded region denotes the GP model 95% confidence interval, showcasing improved alignment between the MF model predictions and actual HF measurements. This enhancement reflects the MF model capacity to more accurately account for discrepancies in LF data through the GP-predicted deviations/corrections.

Overall, while traditional models offer simplicity, dynamic models provide richer insights. The results empha-

Table 2. Comparison of model performance metrics across predictive approaches.

Comparison	Training RMSE	Testing RMSE
\mathbf{y}_{HF} to \mathbf{y}_{LF}	0.63	0.80
\mathbf{y}_{HF} to $\hat{\mathbf{y}}_{\text{HF}}$	0.18	1.01
\mathbf{y}_{HF} to \mathbf{y}_{LF}	0.52	0.91
\mathbf{y}_{HF} to $\hat{\mathbf{y}}_{\text{MF}}$	0.31	0.38

size that MF modeling approaches noticeably enhance predictive accuracy compared to both dynamic LF and standard HF models, leading to a more reliable prediction of the dependent variable. Furthermore, the careful selection of input variables, guided by both quantitative analysis and qualitative insights from industrial partners, plays a critical role in ensuring the model effectiveness and alignment with real-world process behavior.

7. CONCLUSION

In this work, we developed a multi-fidelity model specifically designed to enhance the accuracy of the online analyzer for isobutane concentration. Our analysis shows that this model successfully corrects discrepancies between online measurements and true laboratory values. The testing results reveal a notable accuracy improvement of 52.50%, significantly enhancing monitoring quality in the operation room. This advancement underscores

the effectiveness of multi-fidelity modeling in refining process control and ensuring reliable operational decisions. Future work will focus on enhancing the Gaussian process implementation by addressing process non-linearities to improve the model's accuracy and robustness.

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